

FIND YOUR EFFECTIVE VALORISATION STRATEGY WITH THE IP4OS TOOLBOX.

FAIR-R²L RUBRIC

Making data FAIR, ready for AI use and Responsibly Licensed

FAIR: The FAIR principles are key to today's research dissemination and exploitation ensuring **F**indability, **A**ccessibility, **I**nteroperability and **R**eusability. However FAIR focuses on the technical capabilities but does not ensure:

- AI-safe usage rights (NC/ND restrictions)
- Responsible handling of personal/sensitive data
- Clear provenance for training and derivatives
- Long-term integrity and repository stewardship

FAIR-R: Today's literature extends FAIR to FAIR-R adding **AI-Readiness** ([source](#)), recognising that FAIR ≠ AI-ready and that AI requires structured, validated, ethically safe data. FAIR-R emphasizes quality, provenance, representativeness, and legal clarity.

FAIR-R²L: IP4OS (developed by [Miller International Knowledge](#)) adds a further crucial dimension: datasets must also be **Responsibly Licensed**, ethically sound, in line with the PID strategy, sustainable and legally ready for reuse in AI and machine learning workflows ([source](#)).

RESPONSIBLE LICENSING CONCEPT REQUIRES

requires:

- Licence must be included with the dataset
- Machine-readable exposure (SPDX, schema.org)
- Needs to explicitly allow AI training & derivatives
- Avoid NC/ND for AI reuse
- Attribute rights clearly

adds:

- Explicit dual-format licensing
- AI-specific suitability & documentation
- Ethics & GDPR lane
- Collection- vs item-level clarity
- PID lineage across splits and models
- Long-term stewardship commitment

